

METHODS AND FORMS OF DETERMINING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPUTER MODELS

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Abstract. Analytical work has been carried out on the methods of improving experimental methods and forms in determining the effectiveness of computer models.

Keywords: Computer models, experiments, distance learning, technological process.

Аннотация. Проведена аналитическая работа по методам совершенствования экспериментальных методов и форм определения эффективности компьютерных моделей.

Ключевые слова: Компьютерные модели, эксперименты, дистанционное обучение, технологический процесс.

To determine the adequacy of computer models, distance learning systems, educational resources for the successful implementation of educational and pedagogical tasks in computer science modeling in lectures, laboratories and practical classes in secondary schools it is important to provide scientific feedback on further improvements.

In this context, the following key aspects will be considered in determining and evaluating the effectiveness of models and educational resources for lectures, practical, laboratory and computer modeling practices:

1. Content, interactivity of educational materials in electronic publications and educational resources for lectures, practical, laboratory practice and computer modeling practice.

2. Scientific description of the study material in computer models, electronic publications and educational resources:

- scientifically accurate representation of basic concepts, laws and theories;
- regularity of incorporation of course-based scientific ideas;
- Analyze the process of abstract thinking in students
- use them to explain various events and happenings;
- fair interpretation of various phenomena, laws and theories;

3. Level of comprehensibility of the description of the material intended for laboratory practice:

-the narrative is appropriate to the students' learning opportunities and age characteristics:
- comprehensibility of the experimental standard, curriculum and new teaching material included in the textbook.

4. Logical connection of educational materials with computer models:

-use different methods of logical thinking (induction, comparison, contrast, inference, different methods of proof) in the presentation of the material:

- balance of practical and theoretical training materials;
- Availability of practical materials to introduce concepts, laws and theories;
- Consistency in the disclosure of learning materials on specific topics;
- Demonstrate the need to introduce key concepts;
- Develop them in the later stages of learning the subject.

5. The content of the tasks selected for laboratory practice;
-compliance of demonstration experiments and laboratory work with the new program;
-Laws of conducting experiments on existing technical means in educational institutions,
etc.

6. Reflection of technological processes in assignments;
- Explain the basics of modern technology related to teaching materials.

7. Division of tasks into main and additional parts:
-The importance of dividing assignments into main and secondary parts,
-The degree to which students use topics designed for further study.

8. Questions, issues and content of practical assignments:
-The level of complexity in the formation of basic concepts, laws and theories in the
formation of students' knowledge, skills and abilities.

9. Quality of visual materials in assignments:
-Graphic and artistic design of the task (drawings, graphs, tables, diagrams, color
illustrations, pictures of scientists, etc.).

10. Assignment language:
expressiveness, conciseness, accuracy, brevity and effectiveness;
use of mathematical apparatus,

The following experimental materials have been prepared for the implementation of
pedagogical experiments:

1. A set of requirements for checking selected assignments.
2. A list of key concepts related to laboratory practice testing.
3. Control test materials to test students' knowledge, skills and abilities.
4. Tests related to experimental assignments to test students' knowledge and skills.
5. Instructions for practical work.
6. Forms of recording test results (question and answer sheets).
7. Questionnaires for teachers and students.

The strength of the knowledge is determined by reviewing the material after a period of
study. For a deeper study of knowledge, this method is combined with a systematic review of the
work of the departmental control system. The purpose of this is to determine the content, level and
strength of students' practical knowledge, practical training and qualifications.

Monitoring is conducted annually to help monitor the dynamics of changes in student
learning in educational institutions. The main topics of the control work consist of questions, issues
and experimental assignments. Doing so will, to a certain extent, determine whether students
understand the entire curriculum. During the year, there are two tests at each stage: one in the
middle of the school year, and the second at the end of the school year for the entire course of this
stage. Each control case is given in several variants. The number of options is determined by the
size of the study material being examined and the purpose of the examination.

Each option has the same difficulty. Assignments are structured in such a way that the
bulk of them can be completed by each student, while the rest will require additional student effort.
The results of the tests are recorded in the form of tables, which are carried out at the site of the
first experiment. Some tests are performed on computers.

The results of the experiments on the verification of assignments for laboratory practice
were as follows:

1. Correspondence of the selected tasks to the SST, the content of the subject:

2. The results of the examination of knowledge, skills and abilities of students of pedagogical practice, testing and control classes:

- general results of pedagogical practice, testing and control classes:
 - students' mastery of basic concepts and laws;
 - practical skills and abilities of students;
 - Assessment of students' knowledge. Suggestions and conclusions for improving the selected tasks.
 - Suggestions for improving the task structure,
 - Suggestions for improving the methodology of teaching materials;
 - Suggestions for improving the scientific nature of the assignment;
 - Suggestions for improving the logic of disclosing the content of the study material:
 - Suggestions for improving the ability to master the material:
 - Suggestions for improving the content and methodology of the experiment:
 - questions and suggestions for improving assignments;
 - Suggestions for strengthening interdisciplinary links; -Suggestions for improving the visual materials: -Suggestions for improving the language of the assignment
- The following methods will be used to test e-publications and educational resources in groups identified as pilot areas: The content of computer models, the main criteria for the compatibility of the physical process under consideration: -physical process; -photo illustrations; animations; laboratory work; -audio fragments; -video fragments; -issues; -dictionaries: additional information.

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